

Polyzwitterionic hydrogels as wound dressings with enzymatic debridement functionality for highly exuding wounds

Konstans Ruseva¹, Petar Nedkov², Radostina Aleksandrova³, Desislav Dinev³, Pavletta Shestakova², Plamen Hristov², Elena Vassileva¹

¹*Laboratory on Structure and Properties of Polymers, Department of Pharmaceutical and Applied Organic Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Sofia University "St. Kl. Ohridski", 1, J. Bourchier blvd., 1164, Sofia, Bulgaria*

²*Institute of Organic Chemistry with center of Phytochemistry, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., Bl. 9, 1113, Sofia, Bulgaria*

³*Institute of Experimental Morphology, Pathology and Anthropology with Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., Bl. 25, 1113, Sofia, Bulgaria*

Abstract

Wound debridement is crucial for the proper wound care as it promotes the fast and efficient wound healing through removal of the necrotic tissue. The latter not only impairs the new healthy tissue formation but also increases the odor and the wound exudate, allowing in this way to bacteria and other harmful foreign invaders to spread and infect the wound. Hydrogels wound dressings are usually applied for promoting the autolytic wound debridement but this is slow and not very efficient process. On the other hand, the enzymatic debridement wound products are either ointments or gels and thus they are easily washed out when used for treating highly exuding wounds. This study is an attempt to combine the enzymatic debridement functionality with the high swelling ability of polyzwitterionic networks and to produce an innovative dressing with debridement functionality for highly exuding wounds' healing. To this purpose, two polyzwitterionic hydrogels were synthesized, poly(sulfobetaine methacrylate) and poly(carboxybetaine methacrylate) ones, which were loaded with the protease *Subtilisin DY* for imparting debridement functionality. ZP hydrogels' swelling ability and mechanical properties were shown to depend on their different propensity to physical network formation. Poly(carboxybetaine methacrylate) hydrogels demonstrated better capacity for wound exudate absorption as well as for exerting higher enzymatic debridement activity. Both ZP hydrogels were shown to be non-cytotoxic which confirms their appropriateness for direct contact with the injured tissues. Thus, the newly developed ZP hydrogels demonstrate the potential to be used as new dressing materials with enzymatic debridement functionality for highly exuding wounds.

Introduction

Wound healing is a complex physiological process which aims to restore the integrity of the skin uppermost and outermost tissues in case of injury. The healing process is divided into three overlapping phases - inflammation, tissue formation and tissue remodeling. The overall function of inflammation is to neutralize any pathogens and bacteria that enter the body through the wound as well as to restore the tissue homeostasis. During the tissue formation phase, the wound area is “rebuilt” with new granulation tissue while the final tissue remodeling stage is associated with the wound’s entire closure.

During the wound healing, the wound area could become overrun with necrotic tissue. Such devitalized skin very often impedes the wound repair as it serves as a reservoir for bacterial growth. Moreover, it contains elevated levels of inflammatory mediators which promote chronic inflammation and impair cellular migration¹. Therefore, debridement is necessary to remove the dead tissue and to promote the fast and efficient wound healing. There are four common types of debridement: autolytic, enzymatic, mechanical and surgical, the first two being the most frequently used during wound care therapy as they are able to remove necrotic material in a safe, selective and efficient way.

Autolysis is the natural process which uses the body’s own enzymes to soften and liquefy the necrotic tissue. All wounds go through autolytic debridement in some extent. It is slow, selective, painless, and noninvasive and could be enhanced by a proper wound moistening. Thus, products that support a moist wound environment, e.g. hydrocolloid and hydrogel wound dressings, can enhance the autolytic debridement. An example for commercially available wound dressing with autolytic debridement functionality is Nu-gel², based on alginate hydrogel which main function is to create a moist wound environment assisting in this way the natural autolytic debridement.

The enzymatic debridement is faster and more effective than the autolysis as it makes use of enzymes as debridement agents, e.g. collagenase, papain, proteolytic enzymes. So far, enzymatic debriding is realized mostly through ointments, e.g. Santyl, and gels, e.g. NexoBrid. Santyl is a collagenase-based ointment which is applicable for debriding both chronic dermal ulcers and severely burned areas. It is fast acting and highly selective as it breaks down only denatured collagen, leaving other proteins unaffected. Santyl collagenase ointment is demonstrated to be more efficient in terms of time for the wound healing³ as well as in terms of its clinical and economic benefits compared to e.g. hydrogel dressings which promote only the autolytic debridement⁴. These investigations confirm the higher effectiveness of the enzymatic as compared to autolytic debridement.

NexoBrid is either powder or gel which debriding functionality is due to concentrate of proteolytic enzymes from the stem of *Ananas comosus* (pineapple plant) enriched in bromelain. It is mainly indicated for burn wounds and is usually used with occlusive dressings that create moist wound environments. The application of NexoBrid, however, lasts 4 h, after

¹ Shi, L., Ermis, R., Lam, K., Cowart, J., Attar, P., & Aust, D. (2009). Study on the debridement efficacy of formulated enzymatic wound debriding agents by in vitro assessment using artificial wound eschar and by an in vivo pig model. *Wound Repair and Regeneration*, 17(6), 853–862. doi:10.1111/j.1524-475x.2009.00545.x

² <http://www.systagenix.co.uk/our-products/hydration/nu-gelandtrade-hydrogel-221>

³ Catherine T. Milne, Armann O. Ciccarelli, Mandie Lassy “A Comparison of Collagenase to Hydrogel Dressings in Wound Debridement” *Wounds: a compendium of clinical research and practice* 22(11):270-274 (2010)

⁴ C. Waycaster, C. T. Milne “Clinical and economic benefit of enzymatic debridement of pressure ulcers compared to autolytic debridement with a hydrogel dressing”, *J Med Econ.* 16(7):976-86 (2013); doi: 10.3111/13696998.2013.807268

that special actions to take up the liquefied tissues are required which makes its application more complicated.

Another commercial enzymatic debriding product, available only in Bulgaria, is the developed by Nedkov et al. Neprolysine gel⁵. Its debriding activity is due to the alkaline protease *Subtilisin DY* and it demonstrates high cleaning rate of the necrotic tissue in wounds with different origin effectively enhancing the wounds' repair.

All these debriding products are not applicable for highly exuding wounds, because the excessive exudate washes out part of the gel/ointment thus reducing their debridement effectiveness. Moreover, special actions have to be taken to remove the liquefied necrotic tissue from the wound as mentioned above. Therefore, the need for developing of more appropriate formulation for enzyme based wound debridement products appears which could overcome these two issues by combining high absorption ability of the excessive exudate and the liquefied necrotic tissue with debridement functionality.

Poly(sulfobetaine methacrylate) (pSBMA) and poly(carboxybetaine methacrylate) (pCBMA) are zwitterionic polymers (ZP) which possess the unique ability to swell more in salt solutions than in pure water due to their zwitterionic nature. As the wound exudate is a salty solution, ZP appear to be very appropriate candidates for highly absorbing wound dressing materials in the case of highly exuding wounds. ZP would be able to absorb the exudate more effectively than the common polyelectrolytes, used as wound dressings nowadays (e.g. alginates) which in salt solution usually shrink due to the screening effect of the ions, the so called polyelectrolyte effect. The wound dressings' shrinkage causes pain and could disrupt the wound healing process causing patients' discomfort. ZP, on the contrary, expand upon swelling in salt solutions. The higher the salt concentration and wound exudate volume, the higher ZP expansion is. Thus, ZP based wound dressings would ensure patients' friendly and comfortable dressings avoiding the problems related to the polyelectrolytes' application as wound dressings.

ZP have another advantage if applied as wound dressings - they are known to resist the non-specific protein adsorption and in this way to prevent bacteria and cells adhesion, i.e. they are materials with excellent antifouling properties^{6,7}. Moreover, they could ensure non traumatic wound dressing change as they would not stick to the wound. ZP are also known to be "smart" polymers as they could reversibly swell and de-swell in response to external stimulus such as temperature, pH, salt concentration, due to their zwitterionic structure⁸. This makes them appropriate wound dressings for wounds that are prone to transform to chronic ones as this transformation is accompanied by change in pH as well as in temperature when inflammation occurs. All these ZP's specific properties are highly favorable for wound healing applications and they have triggered the recent interest towards ZP applications in this

⁵ Topalov, I., Fichev, G., Nedkov, P. (1999). Treatment of purulent, necrotic and atonic wounds with necrolytin. *Comptes rendues de l'Academie bulgare des Sciences*. Tome 53, No 4, 2000. *Medecine pharmacology*.

⁶ Cheng, G., Xue, H., Zhang, Z., Chen, S., & Jiang, S. (2008). A Switchable Biocompatible Polymer Surface with Self-Sterilizing and Nonfouling Capabilities. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 47(46), 8831–8834. doi:10.1002/anie.200803570

⁷ Li, G., Cheng, G., Xue, H., Chen, S., Zhang, F., & Jiang, S. (2008). Ultra low fouling zwitterionic polymers with a biomimetic adhesive group. *Biomaterials*, 29(35), 4592–4597. doi:10.1016/j.biomaterials.2008.08.021

⁸ Jiang SY, Cao ZQ (2010) Ultralow-fouling, functionalizable, and hydrolyzable zwitterionic materials and their derivatives for biological applications. *Adv Mater* 22:920–932

area^{9,10,11,12}. However, the ZP's potential as wound dressing materials is still far from being fully explored. For example, ZP could provide a more appropriate carrier for the alkaline protease *Subtilisin DY* immobilization to be utilized for wound enzymatic debridement as it could additionally impart/promote autolytic debridement being also a hydrogel.

The aim of the current study was to develop ZP hydrogels based wound dressings for enzymatic debridement of chronic wounds taking advantage of the proteolytic enzyme *Subtilisin DY*. To this purpose, two types of ZP, polysulfobetaine and polycarboxybetaine, hydrogels have been synthesized and characterized in terms of their swelling ability and mechanical performance. The ZP hydrogels were loaded with alkaline protease *Subtilisin DY* and the enzyme loading efficiency and activity were evaluated. The *Subtilisin DY* loaded ZP hydrogels were *in vitro* tested for their cytotoxicity.

Experimental part

Materials

The monomers N-(3-Sulfopropyl)-N-(methacryloxyethyl)-N,N-dimethylammonium betaine (SBMA) and N,N-Dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate, as well as, the crosslinking agent poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate (PEGDA) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. K₂S₂O₈ (≥99 %) was purchased from Chem Lab. Na₂S₂O₅ (≥97 %) and (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ (≥98 %) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Ethylmethylketon (≥99 %) was purchased from Fluka. β-propiolactone was purchased from Alfa Aesar. Ethylene glycol and ethanol were purchased from Laborchemie Apolda. Human serum albumin was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Subtilisin DY was kindly provided by the Institute of Organic Chemistry with Center of Phytochemistry, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. Casein Hammarsten bovine was purchased from Merck. Tris hydrochloride (≥99 %) was purchased from Labscan. NaCl (≥99 %) and NaOH (≥99 %) were purchased from Chim Spectar. HClO₄ (≥70 %) and H₃PO₄ (≥85 %) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Distilled water used in all experiments was purified using a Millipore water purification system with a minimum resistivity of 18.0 MΩ·m. All reagents were used as received.

Synthesis of ZP hydrogels

Synthesis of poly(sulfobetaine methacrylate) (pSBMA) networks

N-(3-Sulfopropyl)-N-(methacryloxyethyl)-N,N-dimethylammonium betaine (SBMA) (1M) and PEGDA with different mol. % in relation to the SBMA monomer (Table 1), were dissolved in distilled water. The crosslinking polymerization was initiated by potassium persulfate (K₂S₂O₈, 0.1 mol.%) and carried out at 60 °C for 6 hours.

After the end of the crosslinking polymerization, the networks were immersed in a large volume of distilled water for 2 weeks and water was changed daily to remove residuals. The waste water was checked by UV in order to ensure that the networks were purified and all

⁹ J. Yang, H. Chen, S. Xiao, M. Shen, F. Chen, P. Fan, M. Zhong, J. Zheng, Salt-responsive zwitterionic polymer brushes with tunable friction and antifouling properties, *Langmuir* 31 (33) (2015) 9125–9133.

¹⁰ P. Mary, D.D. Bendejacq, M.P. Labeau, P. Dupuis, Reconciling low- and high-salt solution behavior of sulfobetaine polyzwitterions, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 111 (27) (2007) 7767.

¹¹ Yeh, L.-H., Tai, Y.-H., Wang, N., Hsu, J.-P., & Qian, S. (2012). Electrokinetics of pH-regulated zwitterionic polyelectrolyte nanoparticles. *Nanoscale*, 4(23), 7575. doi:10.1039/c2nr32277c

¹² Schneider, L. A., Korber, A., Grabbe, S., & Dissemond, J. (2006). Influence of pH on wound-healing: a new perspective for wound-therapy? *Archives of Dermatological Research*, 298(9), 413–420. doi:10.1007/s00403-006-0713-x

residuals were removed. In this way, PSBMA networks with different crosslinking density were obtained, as revealed in Table 1.

Table 1. Designation of pSBMA networks.

Designation	0.1pSBMA	0.5pSBMA	1pSBMA	2pSBMA	3pSBMA	4pSBMA
PEGDA mol.%	0.1	0.5	1	2	3	4

Synthesis of the CBMA Monomer

The carboxybetaine methacrylate (CBMA) monomer was synthesized using a procedure described elsewhere¹³. Briefly, β -propiolactone (7.2 g) was dissolved in methyl ethyl ketone (10 g) and the resulting solution was slowly added under stirring to a solution of N,N-Dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate (15.7 g) in methyl ethyl ketone (10 g). The reaction mixture was stirred at -10 °C for 3h then left at 0 °C for 12 h. White precipitate was obtained and washed with 500 ml anhydrous ether then dried under reduced pressure to give the final product (95 % yield).

Synthesis of pCBMA networks

The synthesis of pCBMA followed the described elsewhere procedure¹⁴. Briefly, CBMA monomer (1M) was dissolved in a mixed solution of ethylene glycol/ethanol/ H₂O (3:1:1 by volume). Different concentrations of the crosslinking agent PEGDA were used in order to obtain pCBMA networks with different crosslinking densities (Table 2). The crosslinking polymerization was initiated by a mixed initiator consisting of 0.664 mol.% sodium metabisulfite (Na₂S₂O₅) and 1.445 mol. % ammonium persulfate, (NH₄)₂S₂O₈, and carried out at 60° for 15 hours. The obtained pCBMA networks are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Designation of pCBMA networks.

Designation	3pCBMA	4pCBMA	5pCBMA	6pCBMA	7pSCBMA
PEGDA mol.%	3	4	5	6	7

To remove the residuals, the pCBMA networks were washed with large amounts of distilled water for two weeks following the procedure described above.

Characterization of pSBMA and pCBMA hydrogels

Equilibrium swelling ratios of pSBMA and pCBMA in water

The equilibrium swelling ratios (ESR) of the ZP networks were determined gravimetrically. To this purpose, disk-shaped and with defined size dry polymer networks were weighted (W_d) and then immersed in distilled water at room temperature (20°C). The weight of the swollen disks was measured for several days until reaching an equilibrium constant value (W_{sw}). The

¹³ Carlos M Samour, Martin L Falxa Betaine copolymers with hydroxyalkylacrylates and hydroxyalkylmethacrylates, United states patent, US3671502 A, Jun 20, 1972

¹⁴ Zheng Zhang , Timothy Chao , Lingyun Liu , Gang Cheng , Buddy D. Ratner & Shaoyi Jiang (2009) Zwitterionic Hydrogels: an in Vivo Implantation Study, Journal of Biomaterials Science, Polymer Edition, 20:13, 1845-1859

equilibrium swelling ratio (ESR) was determined by the ratio of the weight of water in the swollen gel to the dry samples' weight using the formula:

$$ESR = (W_{sw} - W_d) / W_d \quad (1)$$

At least three pieces from each sample were used to determine their ESR and the obtained values were averaged.

Elastic modulus of ZP hydrogels

The elastic moduli (EM) of pSBMA and pCBMA hydrogels at their ESR were evaluated by using the Hertz contact theory¹⁵. To this purpose, two different loads - metal balls with radii r_1 and r_2 , $r_1 < r_2$, were used. Each ball was placed on the hydrogel surface, the load inducing deformation on the polymer flat surface (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Geometry of the contact between the load and the polymer hydrogel flat surface.

The depth of the obtained curvature (D in Scheme 1) was measured 20 times by cathetometer and the values were averaged. The obtained D average value was used to calculate the elastic modulus, E, of each hydrogel using the following equations:

$$\sigma = (w \cdot g) / S \quad (2)$$

$$E = (9/16) \cdot (r \cdot w \cdot g) / R_{\text{contact}}^3 \quad (3)$$

where σ is the stress, r is the radius of the metal ball used for the measurement, w is the weight of the ball, g is the gravity acceleration and E is the EM of the hydrogel.

Microhardness

The dry ZP samples were indented at room temperature by microhardness tester with a Vicker's diamond pyramidal indenter having a square base and 136° pyramidal angle, attached to a LEICA VMHT universal research microscope. The Vickers' microhardness was calculated using the equation:

$$H_v = \frac{1,8544 \cdot P}{d^2} \text{ [kg} \cdot \text{mm}^{-2}] \quad (4)$$

where P is the load [kg.f] and d is the diagonal of indentation mark [mm] left after the indentation. The indentation duration was 16 s for all measurements. For each sample three different loads were used, for each load at least ten indentations were made at different places of the polymer surface, and then the Vicker's microhardness was calculated using formula (4).

¹⁵ U.D. Schwarz "A generalized analytical model for the elastic deformation of an adhesive contact between a sphere and a flat surface" J. Coll.&Interface Sci. 261 (2003) 99–106

Enzyme loading in pSBMA and pCBMA hydrogels

Calibration curve for protein concentration determination

0.1 g human serum albumin (HSA) was dissolved in 10 ml distilled water and pH of the solution was adjusted to 7.6 using H₃PO₄/NaOH. The absorbance of the stock solution was measured at 280 nm. Several dilutions of the stock solution with distilled water were made and the absorbance of the obtained solutions at the same wavelength was determined. The lowest concentration of HSA used for the calibration curve was 0.002 g/ml. The standard calibration curve was obtained as the measured absorbance values were plotted against the known concentration of the HSA's solutions (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Calibration curve for protein concentration determination obtained with HSA.

The calibration curve is described by the following equation:

$$Y = 0.098 + 71.55 * X \quad (R^2 = 0.99889) \quad (5).$$

The calibration curve equation was used to determine the protein (enzyme) concentration of the solution used for ZP hydrogels loading. To this purpose, 10 μ l from the stock protease solution were diluted in 2.7 ml distilled water and the absorbance of the obtained solution was measured. Using the calibration curve (Figure 1, equation 5), the concentration of protease in the stock solution was determined to be 0.813 mg/ml.

Enzyme immobilization in ZP hydrogels

The enzyme loading in pSBMA and pCBMA hydrogels was performed as disk-shaped samples from both networks with defined size were incubated in the stock enzyme solution with concentration 0.813 mg/ml at 4 °C. The absorption of the enzyme solution where the loading was carried out was measured for pSBMA at the 24th and the 48^h hours after the polymer samples immersion using an appropriate dilution in order to fit to the concentration range of the calibration curve. For pCBMA, due to its higher swelling ability, longer time was used as 48 h was not enough to reach a constant weight, i.e. the measurements were performed at the 24th and the 66th hours. The efficiency of enzyme loading (EEL) for each ZP hydrogel was calculated using the formula:

$$EEL = (m_0 - m_t) \cdot 100 / m_0 \quad (6)$$

where m_0 is the enzyme weight in the stock solution and m_t is the enzyme weight in the solution left after ZP loading.

Enzyme activity of the protease loaded in ZP hydrogels

Determination of the enzyme activity in the stock protease solution

To determine the enzyme activity in the stock solution (liqueur) two independent measurements were performed. For each measurement, three tubes were used, each of them incubated in aqueous bath at 37.5 ± 0.2 °C (Table 3). In tube 1, the reaction between the enzyme and its substrate sodium caseinate was carried out. To this purpose, 2.5 ml 3 wt. % solution of sodium caseinate, 1.5 ml Tris buffer and 45.6 μ l from the enzyme liqueur were poured in tube 1. In each of tube 2 and tube 3, 3 ml 70 wt % solution of H_3PO_4 were poured and they were used to “freeze” the enzyme reaction at two defined times – at the 1st min (control sample) and at the 30th minute after the start of the enzyme-catalysed reaction.

Table 3. Measurement of protease activity – 3 tubes content

Tube №	Reactants	Process
1st tube	2.5 ml 3 wt.% aqueous solution of sodium caseinate; 1.5 ml TRIS buffer; 45.6 μ l enzyme liqueur	enzyme-catalyzed reaction
2nd tube	3 ml 70 % solution of H_3PO_4	control sample
3rd tube	3 ml. 70 % solution of H_3PO_4	enzyme-catalysed reaction that took place for 30 min

The content of tube 1 was agitated for 1 minute and 2 ml aliquot was taken from tube 1 and transferred to tube 2. Then, the contents of tube 1 and tube 2 were agitated for 31 minutes and again 2 ml aliquot was taken again from tube 1 and transferred to tube 3. Tubes 2 and 3 were heated in an aqueous bath at 37°C and agitated for 30 minutes more. Then, both tubes were left at room temperature for 30 minutes and were centrifuged for 15 minutes at 14750 rpm. 250 μ l from each solution were diluted in 2 ml distilled water each.

The absorbance of the obtained solutions was read at 280 nm. The enzyme activity was calculated using following equation:

$$A = 3.156 \cdot \Delta E_{280} \quad (7)$$

where A is the activity of the enzyme in CTA units per ml (one CTA unit is defined as the amount of enzyme that is required to hydrolyze casein to give 1 μ g of tyrosine in 1 min at 37.5 °C), while ΔE_{280} is the difference between the absorbance read after the 31st min and the absorbance read after the 1st min from the beginning of the enzyme-catalyzed reaction.

Determination of the enzyme activity when loaded in PZI hydrogel

The same procedure as described above was repeated by using pSBMA and pCBMA hydrogels loaded with enzyme instead of enzyme liquor. Again, three independent tubes were incubated in water bath at 37.5 ± 0.2 °C. The swollen hydrogel loaded with the protease was immersed in tube 1, which contained 2.5 ml 3 wt.% solution of sodium caseinate and 1.5 ml Tris buffer. The solution was constantly agitated for 1 minute and after that 2 ml aliquot was

taken and poured in 3 ml 70 % solution of H₃PO₄ (tube 2). After 31 minutes of agitation of both tubes, a new aliquot of 2 ml from tube 1 was transferred to tube 3. Then, tubes 2 and 3 were agitated for 30 more minutes at 37.5±0.2 °C and finally left at room temperature for 30 minutes. Both solutions were centrifuged for 15 minutes at 14750 rpm. Their absorbance was measured at 280 nm and used for evaluation of the enzyme activity using formula (7). Three independent measurements with three different enzyme loaded hydrogel pieces were performed for each ZP network and the results were averaged.

The enzyme activity (EA) of the protease loaded in the ZP hydrogels was used to calculate the relative enzymatic activity after loading into the hydrogels:

$$EA [\%] = (E_{a1}/E_{a0}) * 100 \quad (8)$$

where E_{a0} is the enzyme activity of the control, i.e. when using enzyme solution (liqueur) and E_{a1} is the enzyme activity of the enzyme loaded in the respective hydrogel.

Cytotoxicity of pSBMA networks

The effect of 2pSBMA and 4pSBMA networks on cell viability and proliferation was examined by MTT (thiazolyl blue tetrazolium bromide) test¹⁶. To this purpose murine embryonic fibroblasts (permanent cell lines BALB/c 3T3 and L929) were used as model systems. The cells were grown as monolayer cultures in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (D-MEM) medium, supplemented respectively with 10% fetal bovine serum, 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin at 37 °C in a humidified CO₂ incubator (Thermo scientific, Hepa class 100). For routine passages, the cells were detached using a mixture of 0.05% trypsin and 0.02% EDTA.

The MTT test was performed as the dry ZP networks were first swollen in sterile distilled water for 48 hours and subsequently soaked in D-MEM medium for several hours. Then, they were cut into small uniform pieces and transferred into a 48-well tissue culture plate where they were sterilized by UV radiation. Cell suspension with density of 5 x 10³ cells per mL was added to each well. The cell-seeded hydrogels were maintained at 37 °C under 5 % CO₂ for 24 and 48 hours. Then, the cells were gently removed by washing several times with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.2). Each hydrogel was finally incubated with a solution of thiazolyl blue tetrazolium bromide in D-MEM (5 mg in 10 mL D-MEM) for 3 hours at 37 °C under 5% carbon dioxide and 95% air (CO₂ incubator), followed by extraction with a mixture of absolute ethanol and DMSO (1:1, vol/vol) to dissolve the blue formazan. Finally, the optical density of the obtained solution was measured at 540 nm.

As a control, suspension of cells, grown in non-modified medium was used.

The cell viability (%) in the presence of each ZP sample was determined relatively to the cell viability found for the control. All results are reported as the mean ± standard error of the mean values obtained from three independent measurements determined using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Evaluation of cytopathological changes in cells incubated with ZP hydrogels

The cells were grown on sterile cover slips in 6-well plates in the presence of pSBMA hydrogels. Non-treated cells served as controls. After 24h and 48h of incubation, the cover

¹⁶ Mosmann, T. (1983). Rapid colorimetric assay for cellular growth and survival: Application to proliferation and cytotoxicity assays. *Journal of Immunological Methods*, 65(1-2), 55–63. doi:10.1016/0022-1759(83)90303-4

slips were removed and the ability of the hydrogels to induce cytopathological changes was assessed using double staining method with acridine orange (AO) and propidium iodide (PI)¹⁷ and the method of Pappenheim (May–Grunwald–Giemsa) according to the standard procedure. The cells were examined by microscope Olympus CK40, CAM 2800-XP.

Results and Discussion

Equilibrium swelling ratio in water of ZP networks

The crosslinking agent concentration influences the ESRs of pSBMA networks into an unexpected way – as the PEGDA concentration increases, the ESR also increases (Figure 1A). This trend could be explained if the hydrophilicity of PEGDA and the UCST behavior of pSBMA are taken into account. The pSBMA chains at temperature below its UCST (~ 40–50°C) are in collapsed state due to the zwitterionic clusters formation, the latter playing the role of thermoresponsive physical network junctions. The incorporation of the very flexible, long (Mn~575, i.e. 10 ethylene glycol monomeric units) and hydrophilic PEGDMA crosslinks disrupts these junctions, so the pSBMA physical network is partially destroyed and ZP hydrogels expand upon PEGDA concentration increase. The higher the PEGDA concentration, the stronger is its influence on the pSBMA swelling behavior. Thus, the crosslinking agent concentration increase results into an increase in the hydrophilicity as well as into the pSBMA physical network disintegration.

Figure 1. ESRs dependence on crosslinking agent, PEGDA, concentration for: (A) pSBMA and (B) pCBMA hydrogels.

The ESRs of pCBMA networks decrease as the crosslinking agent concentration increases (Figure 1B). This trend could be explained by the pCBMA network density increase upon the PEGDA concentration increase. The comparison between pSBMA and pCBMA swelling ratios shows several times higher swelling ability of the latter as compared to the former. Thus, one could conclude that in pCBMA the physical junctions (i.e. the zwitterionic clusters) number is significantly lower as compared to the pSBMA. This conclusion is in agreement with the reported by Shao et al¹⁸ higher number and longer lifetime of zwitterionic clusters in

¹⁷ Abdel Wahab S. I., A. B. Abdul, A. S. Alzubairi, M. M. Elhassan, S. Mohan. J. Biomed. Biotechnol., 2009, 2009, 46–55.

¹⁸ Q. Shao, L. Mi, X. Han, T. Bai, S. Liu, Y. Li, S. Jiang “Differences in Cationic and Anionic Charge Densities Dictate Zwitterionic Associations and Stimuli Responses”; dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp503473u; J. Phys. Chem. B 2014, 118, 6956–6962

polysulfobetaines (PSB) as compared to the polycarboxybetaines (PCB). According to the authors, the reason is that PSB possess cationic and anionic groups that match better in charge density than the cationic and anionic groups in the PCB. Thus, the zwitterionic moieties propensity to form clusters (physical junctions) in PSB is higher as compared to the ones in PCB and as a result less inter-chain zwitterionic associations are formed in PCB as compared to PSB. The lower propensity of PCB to form physical network defines the lack of temperature responsivity for this ZP.

PEGDA crosslinking imparts chemical crosslinks between pCBMA macromolecules which limit the swelling ability of the network and increase the overall network density, i.e. result into an ESR decrease (Figure 1B). The chemical network controls the pCBMA swelling behavior in contrast to the case of pSBMA where the role of the physical network prevails.

Elastic modulus of pSBMA and pCBMA hydrogels at their ESR

The pSBMA and pCBMA' elastic moduli dependence on the PEGDA concentration confirms the conclusions made from their swelling behavior in water (Figure 2). It is known that the elastic modulus of a network is proportional to the number of network junctions (chemical and/or physical).

Figure 2. Elastic modulus as determined by the Hertz contact theory for: (A) pSBMA and (B) pCBMA hydrogels at their equilibrium swelling.

The pSBMA elastic modulus decreases with the crosslinking agent concentration increase (Figure 2A). This trend well corresponds to the PSBMA physical junctions' disintegration due to the PEGDA chemical crosslinking, discussed above (Figure 1A).

The pCBMA network density increase, due to the PEGDMA chemical crosslinking (Figure 1B), is accompanied by the pCBMA elastic modulus increase (Figure 2B). The chemical crosslinks formed by the PEGDA beside limiting the pCBMA swelling also result into an increase in their hydrogels elastic moduli. The effect gets more pronounced as the crosslinking agent concentration increases (Figure 2B).

Thus, there is a very good correspondence between the swelling behavior and the elastic modulus for pSBMA and pCBMA.

Microhardness

The polymer networks' crosslinking density affects their microhardness in a similar to the EM way – the higher the number of network junctions, the higher the microhardness is. The pSBMA microhardness decreases as the PEGDA concentration increases (Figure 3A) which is in agreement with the observed elastic modulus decrease (Figure 2A) and swelling ratio increase (Figure 1A). All these dependencies are due to the physical network disruption and decrease of the pSBMA physical network density. On the contrary, the pCBMA microhardness increases upon the PEGDA concentration increase (Figure 3B), similarly to its elastic modulus behaviour (Figure 2B), due to the increase in the chemical crosslinking density.

Figure 3. Microhardness as a function of the crosslinking agent PEGDA concentration for: (A) pSBMA and (B) pCBMA dry networks.

In summary, the three properties of ZP networks – ESR, elastic modulus and microhardness, show that the PEGDA concentration increase results into (i) loosening of pSBMA total (physical+chemical) network due to the physical network disintegration and increasing its hydrophilicity in contrast to (ii) the pCBMA network which density increases and thus defines also an increase in the elastic modulus and microhardness. The PEGDA concentration could be used to control the ZP networks density and hence to finely tune the ZP hydrogels performance as matrices for enzyme immobilization.

Subtilisin DY loading in ZP hydrogels

The ZP hydrogels were loaded with *Subtilisin DY* in order to impart a debridement function in relation to their planned application as wound dressings. Physical entrapment was chosen as a method for the *Subtilisin DY* loading into the ZP hydrogels as this method is simple, does not change the intrinsic enzyme properties and does not involve any chemical modification¹⁹.

The *Subtilisin DY* loading (entrapment) in pSBMA and pCBMA hydrogels was estimated in relation to their application as functional wound dressings (Figure 4). For both ZP hydrogels, the *Subtilisin DY* loading does not strongly depend on the PEGDA concentration when long

¹⁹ A. Dwevedi „Basics of Enzyme Immobilization Enzyme Immobilization”, Springer International Publishing Switzerland 2016; DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-41418-8_2

enough loading times were used. For pSBMA hydrogels, 48 h loading time was enough to attain an equilibrium enzyme loading of ~ 45-50% for all studied networks (Figure 4A). For pCBMA hydrogels, the enzyme loading was 55-60% after 66 h loading time (Figure 4B). The longer loading time needed for pCBMA hydrogels to attain an equilibrium enzyme loading is related to their higher swelling ability as compared to pSBMA networks (Figure 1).

Figure 4. Enzyme loading for: (A) pSBMA and (B) pCBMA.

pSBMA hydrogels show a lower enzyme loading (by ~10-15%) as compared to the pCBMA ones and this could be related to the enzyme loading dependence on the ZP network density, as the loading is a diffusion controlled process.

Enzyme activity

The enzyme immobilization allows the enzyme re-use for an extended period of time as well as it enables an easier separation of the catalyst (enzyme) from the product²⁰. With respect to the envisaged wound dressing functionalization, the *Subtilisin DY* entrapment into ZP hydrogel aims to keep the enzyme active over the period of the wound dressing application and then to easily remove it from the wound when its usage is not needed anymore, i.e. when no further wound debridement is required. Thus, the *Subtilisin DY* entrapment in ZP hydrogels is the way to ensure the debridement enzyme activity of the hydrogels dressings for the period when wound debridement is needed.

For both ZP hydrogels, the *Subtilisin DY* activity gradually decreases as the number of activity measuring cycles increases but the enzyme preserves a high overall preserves even at the last 6th cycle. The enzyme activity drops from 100% down to ~50% at the 6th cycle when the enzyme is loaded into pCBMA hydrogels. The pCBMA hydrogels having looser network (Figure 5B) preserve the enzyme activity to ~60% event at the last, 6th cycle, which means that the hydrogels could ensure high debridement activity during the while time period of application as wound dressings. The activity of the enzyme loaded into pSBMA drops from ~60% down to ~ 30% as the number of cycles increases (Figure 5A). The access of the enzyme loaded into the hydrogel to the casein substrate is limited in pSBMA and much easier in pCBMA due to the latter's higher swelling ability in aqueous media. Thus, the mass transfer

²⁰ M.S. Mohy Eldin, D.G. Mita "Immobilized Enzymes: Strategies for Overcoming the Substrate Diffusion-Limitation Problem", Current Biotechnology, 2014, 3, 207-217

limitations and the presence of diffusional constraints, which are concomitant to the enzyme entrapment into a matrix, play more significant role in pSBMA than in pCBMA hydrogels. The substrate molecules diffusion into the pSBMA matrix is limited which is expected to affect the maximum rate of the enzyme reaction, V_{\max} (the rate of the reaction when the enzyme is saturated with substrate) as well as the Michaelis constant, K_m , which is the concentration of the substrate which permits the enzyme to achieve half V_{\max} .

Figure 5. Enzyme activity of *Subtilisin DY* loaded into: (A) pSBMA and (B) pCBMA hydrogels.

While for pSBMA hydrogels, the PEGDA crosslinking does not show a clear trend for influencing the loaded enzymes' activity, for pCBMA hydrogels such trend is visible. The enzyme loaded into the densest pCBMA network (6pCBMA) exhibits the lowest activity for all 6 cycles as compared to the other pCBMA networks. This is another proof that the casein (substrate) diffusion is more difficult in the denser network and thus the lowest enzyme activity among all pCBMA hydrogels is observed here. Thus, the hydrogel network density affects the pCBMA performance as a matrix for the enzyme immobilization.

The enzyme leakage is a well known disadvantage of the enzyme immobilization via physical entrapment and it could be partially responsible for the observed decrease in the *Subtilisin DY* activity (Figure 5). However, the enzyme leakage does not negatively affect the planned ZP hydrogels application as wound dressings because the *Subtilisin DY* which diffuses out from the hydrogel will go to the wound and would realize its debridement function there. For example, recently a silicon based dried emulsion for controlled release of proteolytic enzymes was introduced as a rapid enzymatic debridement device for cutaneous wounds treatment²¹.

In summary, *Subtilisin DY* activity when loaded into ZP hydrogels could ensure the wound enzymatic debridement during the wound dressing lifetime ensuring at the same time an effective wound exudate absorption due to its hydrogel nature.

Cytotoxicity of pSBMA networks

The pSBMA hydrogels could be evaluated as non-cytotoxic as the cell viability in their presence is comparable and even higher to the viability of the cells in the control (Figure 6).

²¹ R. Bott, J. Crissman, C. Kollar, M. Saldajeno, G. Ganshaw, X. Thomas, T. H. Lane, P. Klykken, J. M. Davidson, L. B. Nanney "A silicone-based controlled-release device for accelerated proteolytic debridement of wounds" *Wound Rep Reg* **15**, 227–235 (2007); DOI:10.1111/j.1524-475X.2007.00209.x

The results do not depend on the crosslinking agent concentration because for all studied PEGDA concentrations (0.1, 1, 2 and 4) the cell viability is around 100% and higher. The higher than 100% cell viability means that the cells incubated with pSBMA hydrogels are in fact better proliferating than the cells in the control which is a further proof of the non cytotoxicity of the ZP hdyrogels.

Figure 6. Cytotoxicity of pSBMA networks: The viability and proliferation of L929 cells as examined by MTT test.

This result is encouraging as the wound dressings will be in a direct contact with the cells of both the injured and the healthy tissues in and around the wound. So, if eventually cytotoxic the ZP hydrogels would not be appropriate as they will cause cell death during the wound healing application.

Evaluation of cytopathological changes in cells that were incubated with ZP hydrogels

In order to evaluate if cells morphology changes upon their incubation with the pSBMA hydrogels, two groups of cells were studied by light microscopy. These are as follows: (i) mouse embryonal fibroblasts (cell line L929) incubated on the bottom of 48-well plaque (Figure 7) and (ii) L929 cells grown on 0.1pSBMA hydrogel (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Optical microscopy of murine embryonal fibroblasts (cell line L929) grown for 72 h on the 48-well plates surface (pictures are taken at different parts of the plates surface) (Microscope Olympus CK40, CAM 2800-XP, 20x).

The microscopic images in Figure 7 clearly show the ability of the cells to adhere on the plates surface and to form monolayers. The cells grown on the bottom of the 48-well plates

have the elongated spindle shape which is characteristic for fibroblasts and form an even dense monolayer due to their good adhesion to the plate surface (Figure 7).

Figure 8. Optical microscope images of murine embryonal fibroblasts (cell line L929) grown on (A) 0.1pSBMA hydrogel and (B) 0.5pSBMA hydrogel (Microscope Olympus CK40, CAM 2800-XP, 20x)

In contrast, the cells grown on both hydrogels surfaces (Figures 8A and B) do not spread on the surface and have round shape growing rather in clusters than in monolayers. This shape change that the cells undergo after incubation with pSBMA hydrogels and their propensity to proliferate in clusters mean that the hydrogels do not provoke cell death. The low bioadhesion that pSBMA is known to possess defines the weaker cell adhesion observed for cells incubated with pSBMA hydrogels as compared to the cells incubated onto the 48-wells plate surface. Moreover, the hydrogels in general provoke low bioadhesion due to the high amount of water that they contain. Thus, the cell monolayer attached to the 48-wells plate surface was difficult to be removed – 4-5-minute-long treatment with a solution containing EDTA and trypsin was needed to remove it. In contrast, the cells attached to the hydrogels surface are partially but not fully attached and some of them could be easily washed out during, for example, the MTT test, due to the fact that they are not strongly attached on the hydrogel surface.

Conclusions

In the present study, ZP hydrogels loaded with *Subtilisin DY* were developed as wound dressings with enzymatic debridement functionality for highly exuding wounds. So far, hydrogels dressings are usually applied for promoting the autolytic debridement but this is a slow process and clinical experience suggests that it is not an effective form of debridement²². On the other hand, the enzymatic debridement wound products are either ointments or gels and cannot be applied effectively for highly exuding wounds. This study is the first attempt to combine the enzymatic debridement functionality with the high swelling ability of ZP networks and to produce an innovative dressing for wound healing. Two ZP networks were studied to this purpose, pCBMA and pSBMA. pCBMA hydrogels demonstrated higher enzyme loading and higher enzyme activity as compared to pSBMA due to their higher swelling ability in aqueous media. The crosslinking density, varied via the crosslinking agent PEGDA concentration, was established to be a tool for controlling the pCBMA hydrogel swelling and hence of the activity of the entrapped inside *Subtilisin DY*. In contrast, for the pSBMA hydrogels, due to their stronger inter-chain interaction and physical network formation, PEGDA concentration was not a powerful tool for exerting similar control. Moreover, the higher swelling capacity of CBMA is another advantage for the planned use of these hydrogels as dressings for highly exuding wound. Both ZP hydrogels ensured high enzyme activity for prolonged time of application, being at the same time non cytotoxic. Thus, these newly developed ZP hydrogels have the potential to be used as new dressing materials with enzymatic debridement functionality for highly exuding wounds, pCBMA demonstrating better potential than pSBMA with respect to the planned application.

Acknowledgements

This study was financially supported by the Bulgarian National Science Foundation under Grant No T 02/15. The support of the Horizon 2020 “Materials Networking” project ID: 692146-H2020-eu.4.b is also acknowledged.

²² C. Moffatt, M. J. Morison, E. Pina “Wound bed preparation for venous leg ulcers” in European Wound Management Association (EWMA). Position Document: Wound Bed Preparation in Practice. London: MEP Ltd, 2004.